

CYCLIC LOADING EFFECTS ON CREASING BEHAVIOR OF SOFT SOLIDS

Z. Li¹, Z. Zhou² and Y. Li, S. Tang^{3*}

¹ College of Materials Science and Engineering, Chongqing University, Chongqing, 400017

² Department of Engineering Mechanics, Chongqing University, Chongqing, 400017

³ Department of Engineering Mechanics, Dalian University of Technology, Dalian, 116024

Keywords: Silicone Rubber, Fatigue, Crease, Finite elements

Elastic surface instability of silicon rubber has been harnessed to realize the recoverable large deformation of flexible electronic for silicones, carbon nanotubes and graphenes. When a homogeneous silicone block is compressed, its smooth surface suddenly folds into a region of self-contact with a sharp tip when a critical strain is attained, thereby forming creases. Despite the abundance of crease formations in scientific and engineering applications, the underlying physics principles emerge only recently with the nature of creases being attributed to the broken symmetry of scale and translation. With this regard, creases can be distinguished from the often discussed wrinkles. When silicone rubber is used in engineering applications, it often experiences cyclic loadings. Thus, a question naturally raises: can cyclic loading influence its surface instability behavior? Under cyclic loading conditions, few studies show that rubbers such as Nitrile Butadiene Rubbers (NBRs) exhibit stress-softening response. However, up-to-date, the effect of cyclic loading on the surface instability of rubber has not been answered. To understand this effect, we need to resort to experiments to study the surface instability after the cyclic loading applied on rubber specimen.

Experimental study on surface instability of silicone rubber under mechanical compression remains difficult and challenging, because barrelling instabilities usually occur at much lower strains, comparing with the critical strain for creasing. To circumvent this issue, researchers have resorted to bend a slab or rod. Nevertheless, quantitative characterization on these geometries is complicated, induced by both nonuniform (inhomogeneous) deformation along the thickness direction of specimens and difficulty of measuring spacing and shapes of the surface folds. The nucleation and growth of creases has been studied by compressing a soft elastomer (Polydimethylsiloxane, PDMS) on a stiff substrate (PDMS) and introducing material variation along thickness direction from the edge to center of the thin film, which can introduce creases to nucleate at the edge and channel towards the center. However, when the substrate is introduced, the measured critical strain and pattern can greatly differ from those of homogeneous soft solids. The consideration of the variation of modulus along thickness direction due to the bilayered structure is also numerically and experimental challenging. Such a barrier can be resolved by developing a in-house loading apparatus. In this study, we experimentally demonstrate that the nucleation and progressing of creases on the surface of a cuboid silicone block subjected to mechanical compressive loading under plane strain conditions can be monitored through this in-house loading apparatus.

Especially, with this in-house loading apparatus at hand, we can study the surface instability after the silicone rubber experiences cyclic loadings. Since the silicon rubber is very soft, we pinch the silicone rubber cyclicly a few times (usually 10 times) by a hand. It is followed by putting the specimen into the loading apparatus. When the imposed compressive strain is around 30%, multiple creases are formed on the top surface. It is extremely surprising because the critical strain for nucleating a single crease on a homogeneous soft solid is around 35% , for wrinkles around 46% given by the classical solution given by Biot. The pattern of the surface creasing is also different from a single or double crease, which is typically observed in our experiments for specimens without cyclic loading. Therefore, it is interesting to probe the underlying mechanisms for the formation of multiple creases.

In this work, we combine experiments and finite element simulations to study the effect of pre-imposed cyclic loading on surface instability of silicon rubber under compression. We first fabricate cuboid blocks of silicon rubber to perform the uniaxial compression under exact plane strain conditions with a homemade apparatus. We pinch the silicone rubber cyclically a few times before we carry out the uniaxial compression test (Figure 1). It is found surprisingly that multiple creases are formed on the surface of silicone rubber (Figure 2), different from what observed in our experiments without the cyclic pinching [1-3]. To reveal the underlying physics for the multiple creases observed, we first perform the detailed nanoindentation experiments to measure the material properties at the different places on the cuboid specimen. It is found that the material property is not uniform and varies with the thickness after the cyclic pinching. A three-layer and multilayered finite element model is then proposed (Figure 3). The different layers are set up with a different property based on the experimental measurement. According to our finite element model and simulations, the experimentally observed multiple creases should be attributed to a thin and stiff layer formed on the surface of silicon rubber after the pre-imposed cyclic loading.

Figure 1: Cyclic loading on a cuboid block of silicone rubber

Figure 2: Surface crease on the silicone rubber under uniaxial compression after cyclic loading.

Figure 3: (a) Schematic for the three-layer FE model. The height for each layer is h_0 , h_1 , and h_2

with modulus E_0 , E_1 and E_2 respectively. (b) Schematic for a multi-layer FE model with 200 layers. The height of the i th layer is h_i with modulus E_i . The height of each layer is equally distributed in the simulations.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Tang, Y. Li, W.K. Liu, X.X. Huang, Surface Ripples of Polymeric Nanofibers under Tension: The Crucial Role of Poisson's Ratio. *Macromolecules* 2014, 47, 6503–6514.
- [2] A. Gent and I. Cho. Surface instabilities in compressed or bent rubber blocks. *Rubber Chem. Technol.* 1999, 72, 253–262.
- [3] A. Ghatak and A.L. Das. Kink instability of a highly deformable elastic cylinder. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 2007, 157 99, 076101.